

A DENTAL VISIT AT THE AGE OF NINE MONTHS

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LETTER TO THE EDITOR

ABSTRACT: *The age of nine months demands a mandatory visit to the pediatrician and the pediatric dentist. This audio transcript gives an overview of what the parent can expect during a routine dental check-up of the infant.*

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Sir,

Apart from its relevance in social and astronomical circles, number nine holds a significant value in biology as well (nine-month old pregnancy). The birth of an offspring after nine months is psychosocially monumental for parents. When the child reaches the age of nine months, not only should the parents start preparing for a visit to the pediatrician, but must also understand the importance of a visit to the pediatric dentist.

A child will generally have one or two primary mandibular incisors present in the oral cavity at the age of nine months. An anticipatory guidance for parents at this stage would be to ensure to clean these two teeth which are present in the oral cavity with a soft finger toothbrush. It is also important to address to all the concerned parents that it is not a mandate for the teeth to erupt during this time. In such a scenario, they are advised to use a gauze piece or a soft cloth to clean the gum pads. Parents are then educated about weaning. The shift in diet from liquids to semi-solids further raises the importance of the oral cavity to be kept clean.¹

It is vital for parents to understand that along with the vaccination schedule a visit to the pediatric dentist must also be scheduled. Thus, these preliminary steps can help in keeping the infant's oral cavity free from any disease.

REFERENCE

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